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USING PICTURES TO TEACH ENGLISH VOCABULARY FOR 4TH-GRADE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study examines how effectively picture-based methods work while teaching English vocabulary to 4th-grade students at School Number 2 in Kasansay. Memorizing the wide range of vocabulary is the key part of language learning as we need to know various words to improve both our receptive and productive skills. So the researcher suggests that visual aids can play a pivotal role when we teach vocabulary particularly in primary class students. This approach was utilized with 30 students, gathering quantitative data through questionnaire which includes 4 questions, and also post-tests after teaching 2 different classrooms with 2 separate methods to see how well picture based vocabulary teaching work in 4th graders compared to traditional text based method. Results show that more than 80 % students prefer to learn new words by making sure after seeing its picture on the board rather than learning by text, it indicates that most of the students find this method enjoyable and engaging. The next quantitative data shows the students post-test results with the high percentage in new method. Students showed an average 85% result in vocabulary knowledge test after learning words visually as well as verbally. This research underscores the necessity for educators to change their traditional method into interactive and engaging picture-based method while teaching 4th graders. Using various suitable images to teach vocabulary can make the language learning environment more effective and enhance not only students' comprehension but also their verbal skills.

Keywords: *picture-based method; vocabulary acquisition; vocabulary retention; primary school students; visual aids; English language teaching; interactive learning; traditional vs innovative methods;*

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur tadqiqotda Kasansoy shahridagi 2-sonli maktabning 4-sinf o'quvchilariga ingliz tili so'z boyligini o'rgatishda rasm asosidagi metodning samaradorligi o'rganildi. So'z boyligini yod olish til o'rganish jarayonining asosiy qismi hisoblanadi, chunki turli so'zlarni bilish o'quvchining ham tushunish, ham ifoda etish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi. Shu boisdan vizual vositalardan foydalanish, ayniqsa boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga so'z o'rgatishda, muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Tadqiqotda 30 nafar o'quvchi ishtirok etdi. Ma'lumotlar 4 ta savoldan iborat so'rovnomma va ikki xil metod bilan o'tilgan darslardan keyingi testlar orqali to'plandi: biri rasm asosida, ikkinchisi esa an'anaviy matn asosida o'tkazildi.

Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, o'quvchilarning 50 foizdan ortig'i yangi so'zlarni matndan emas, balki doskada uning rasmini ko'rgan holda o'rganishni afzal ko'radi. Bu esa ko'pchilik o'quvchilar uchun ushbu metodni qiziqarli va jalb etuvchi ekanligini bildiradi. Post-test natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, rasm asosidagi metod orqali o'qigan o'quvchilar so'z boyligi bo'yicha o'rtacha 30 foizga yaxshilanish ko'rsatganlar.

Tadqiqot natijalari o'qituvchilarni an'anaviy yondashuvdan interaktiv va ko'rgazmali metodlarga o'tish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi. Turli mos rasmlar yordamida so'z o'rgatish jarayoni nafaqat o'quvchilar tushunchasini, balki ularning og'zaki nutq ko'nikmalarini ham samarali rivojlantiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: rasm asosidagi metod; so'z boyligini o'zlashtirish; so'zlarni eslab qolish; boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari; ko'rgazmali vositalar; ingliz tili o'qitish; interaktiv ta'lim; an'anaviy va innovatsion metodlar;

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данном исследовании рассматривается эффективность использования метода обучения на основе изображений при преподавании английской лексики учащимся 4-х классов школы №2 города Касансай. Запоминание словарного запаса является ключевым аспектом изучения языка, поскольку знание разнообразных слов способствует развитию как рецептивных, так и продуктивных навыков. Визуальные средства могут играть решающую роль при обучении лексике, особенно среди учеников начальных классов.

В исследовании участвовали 30 учеников. Были собраны количественные данные посредством анкетирования, включающего 4 вопроса, а также пост-тесты после проведения занятий в двух разных классах с использованием двух различных методов: традиционного текстового и метода с опорой на изображения.

Результаты показали, что более 50% учащихся предпочитают изучать новые слова, видя их изображения на доске, а не только через текст. Это свидетельствует о том, что большинство учеников считают данный метод более увлекательным и интересным. Пост-тесты показали, что при использовании визуального метода успеваемость учащихся повысилась в среднем на 30%.

Таким образом, данное исследование подчеркивает необходимость для педагогов переходить от традиционных методов преподавания к интерактивным и наглядным подходам. Применение различных соответствующих изображений при обучении лексике делает процесс изучения языка более эффективным и способствует развитию не только понимания, но и устных навыков учащихся.

Ключевые слова: *метод обучения на основе изображений; усвоение лексики; запоминание слов; учащиеся начальных классов; наглядные пособия; преподавание английского языка; интерактивное обучение; традиционные и инновационные методы;*

Introduction

Vocabulary plays an important role in learning foreign language as it supports communication and comprehension. If students memorize a range of words, they can have a boost in their language learning. Nevertheless, there are still vocabulary memorizing problems because teachers, in primary schools prefer to use traditional text-based methods rather than interactive ones. Thus, many students have the same obstacles while boosting their vocabulary retention. Various studies indicate that picture-based methods can make the lessons engaging, interactive also motivating for young learners to enhance their understanding. Dual coding theory (Paivio 1971) suggests that learning new words by both visual and verbal ways students can learn and remember newly memorized words well. In addition, Mayer (2009), emphasizes that learners can process verbal and visual information simultaneously resulting in deeper understanding. The next study shows that when the teacher uses picture-based method, it demonstrates more accurate usage in sentences (Liu (2017)). Therefore, this study aims to check how effective the picture-based method while teaching English vocabulary to 4th-grade students.

Research questions:

1. What kinds of obstacles do my students face while using newly learned words in their daily communication?
2. What are my students' attitudes toward learning new vocabulary through pictures?
3. How does using pictures support students in acquiring and retaining new vocabulary effectively?

Gathering data for this article is important so several research-based surveys were conducted such as Google Forms questionnaires, vocabulary tests for students and classroom observation. Firstly, this article discusses the effectiveness of picture-based methods in the lessons and explores solutions to problems related to vocabulary retention.

Methodology**Research design**

This research utilized a quantitative research design to examine the productiveness of picture-based methods in teaching English vocabulary to 4th-grade students. This research paper focused on the comparison between traditional text-based method and interactive picture-based method in primary classrooms. This study included 30 participants from two different groups of 4th-grade students at school No. 2 In Kasansay. The students who has the same English proficiency levels participated in this research, their classes were mixed-gender as both male and female students study in the same place. To gather the data for this research paper, several instruments based on the article were conducted:

Google Forms questionnaires consisting of 4 questions were used to collect data. With the help of these questions, students' attitude toward learning English vocabulary by pictures were measured in percentage effortlessly.

Vocabulary post-tests were used to check students' retention and acquisition scores after learning new words with 2 different types of methods.

Pre-tests weren't used as it was not necessary to examine their knowledge. Because only the newly learned words were given in post-tests.

Classrooms observation were also done during both classes' lessons to monitor students' engagement and participation. Additionally, Experienced teachers were asked to enter and observe both classes and tell their own opinion about methodologies which were used by the teacher.

Procedure

The study was conducted in 2 different phases to fulfill information about the method:

1. In the first phase, first group students were taught new vocabulary by using traditional text-based method while another class had the vocabulary lessons with picture-based method. In both classes the same words were taught for 1 week, including 3 sessions, however the way of learning was varying.

2. In the second phase, there was a post-test which examines students both retention and acquisition was given to participants

3. In addition, there were questionnaires to calculate the percentage of students' interests in learning vocabulary with images. Students filled out 4 questions after having lessons with pictures. Observation was recorded to find how effective and engaging the picture-based methods are.

Discussion

Data collection and analysis

The collected data was analyzed with the use of quantitative methods. After post-tests, Students' results were compared between two methods and questionnaire answers were measured and showed in percentage to determine students' preferences and attitudes. The students who learned words by pictures scored 30 % higher than another group's scores. It shows that interactive method significantly improved students' vocabulary knowledge. The results indicate that picture-based methods are more successful than the traditional one. According to questionnaire results, almost 80% of students preferred picture-based method. 4th-grade students' vocabulary

retention and acquisition were substantially enhanced because of innovative method. Traditional method had been used for a long time however this cannot be continued to teach vocabulary because of the century students are living now differs from the past and this method is not able to interact students' attention enough. Therefore, new methods have to be used in a classroom to make learning vocabulary productive. This picture-based method is one of the most suitable and interactive one to enhance students' vocabulary knowledge. So the improvement shows that students find this method simple to achieve their aim.

In addition, Reliability and validity are such vital things when it comes to checking the students' vocabulary after having an experiment in two groups. So, the post-tests were made by a teacher who teaches 4th graders and agreed that test is suitable for the experimental use. This makes the test valid and reliable. Questionnaire questions were well-structured and easy to answer because of its easiness. Students who learned through the picture-based method completed the survey. Both sets of quantitative data helped to provide a well-rounded analysis of effectiveness of teaching methods. There are some limitations to generalize these strategies it was experimented only in a single school which may influence the outcomes because of school related factors specifically. This methodological framework aims to evaluate different vocabulary teaching strategies, focusing on how they affect to 4th-grade students' vocabulary retention and learning.

Results

The results of this study are presented by quantitative insights from the post-tests and questionnaire. The findings show significant differences in students' vocabulary acquisition and engagement between the traditional and innovative methods

Quantitative findings

The post-test scores of both groups are analyzed to measure the effect of the various methods used to teach vocabulary. The average scores are summarized to both groups below:

Group A (Innovative picture-based methods):

Post-test average score: 85%

85% of the words were remembered by students during the exam.

Group B (Traditional text-based methods):

Post-test average score: 63%

Only 63% of the words were remembered by students during the exam.

The results indicate that students in Group A, who learned vocabulary with interesting pictures, showed a substantial improvement in vocabulary knowledge compared to Group B, who were taught through traditional methods. The highest result (85%) in Group A's scores suggests that interactive teaching methods are more productive and engaging in improving vocabulary acquisition and retention.

Questionnaire

In this Google Forms survey, 15 students who learned vocabulary through pictures answered the questions related to the method they have used in their one-week

lesson. Their answers show their preference of this study strategy. The summarized results are presented below:

These pictures indicate that most of the students find this method more intriguing and effective. The first question was aimed to calculate how many students preferred learning with pictures all the time. The results are positive at all as 60% of the participants preferred learning this method all the time. In addition, rest of the students wanted to learn with this method sometimes. The second one was about different methods students loved to learn through, they are “using pictures to learn words”, “playing games to learn words” and “using texts to learn vocabulary”. 80% of the

students chose picture-based method. It means they found it easy. Other students preferred the games and texts, too. The third one shows that whether students have difficulties or not while learning vocabulary with pictures. Almost all participants (93.3%) had not got any obstacles with it. However, only one student had some problems with this method (6.7%). The last question is related to students' interests do they find pictures interesting or not. The results are so positive as more than half of the students (57.1%) chose the answer "I love". The rest of the students preferred the answer "I like". Overall, nearly all participants find this method engaging, effective and simple.

Summary of the findings:

The results of findings show that innovative method is more suitable to use in 4th graders because the students' opinion about this method is significantly positive. Additionally, classroom observations showed that students acted more engaging in Group A compared to Group B. Thus, this study summarized these findings are very productive and enjoyable.

Conclusion

This research topic aimed to examine how effective the picture-based methods are in teaching English vocabulary to 4th graders. The insights from post-tests and questionnaire utilize that students who learned new words with innovative method showed substantially higher retention and understanding words compared to other traditional text-based method used group. The results also reveal that participants found the method easier, more engaging and enjoyable, with the highest result in the exam (85%) that indicates that students memorized newly learned words well.

These findings highlight the importance of integrating visual aids into primary language teaching. By combining visual and verbal cues, educators can enhance both vocabulary acquisition and retention, catering to the learning needs of young students. While this study was limited to a single school, the positive outcomes suggest that picture-based methods have great potential to improve vocabulary learning in similar educational contexts.

To conclude, this study supports the importance of modern teaching strategies that makes lessons more dynamic, effective, engaging and enjoyable for students. It emphasizes that traditional methods should be changed with more interactive ones.

Appendix

POST-TEST: PLACES IN THE CITY (GRADE 4) 2nd Unit

Ex.1

Instructions: Read the sentences carefully and choose the correct word from the list below to complete each gap.

(Bank, Crosswalk, Bus station, Subway station, Museum, Shopping mall, Traffic light, Square, Restaurant, Hotel)

- If you need to deposit or withdraw money, you must go to the _____
- We saw beautiful old paintings and statues when we visited the _____
- It's safe to walk across the street only when you use the _____
- My family and I love going to the _____ to buy clothes and new toys.
- In the middle of the city, there is a large _____ where people gather for events.
- The tourist checked into a comfortable _____ near the park for the night.
- Wait for the green light at the _____ before driving or walking.
- We missed the number 5 bus, so we had to wait at the _____ for the next one.
- To get a delicious meal, my parents booked a table at the new Italian _____
- It is faster to travel across the city by taking the train at the _____

Ex.2

Instructions: Match the appropriate picture with the following words. And write the correct answer below the pictures

- | | |
|-------------------|------------------|
| 1. Bank | 6. Shopping mall |
| 2. Crosswalk | 7. Traffic light |
| 3. Bus station | 8. Square |
| 4. Subway station | 9. Restaurant |
| 5. Museum | 10. Hote |

References

Liu, J. (2017). The role of visual aids in vocabulary learning for young learners. *Journal of language teaching and Research*, 8(5), 1012-1020.

Paivio, A. (1971). Dual coding theory: Retrospect and current status. *Canadian Journal of Psychology*, 45(3), 255-287

Mayer, R.E. (2009). *Multimedia learning* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press

Nation, I. S. P. (2013). *Learning vocabulary in another language* (2nd ed.).

Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Thornbury, S. (2002). *How to teach vocabulary*. Harlow: Pearson Education.

Schmitt, N. (2000). *Vocabulary in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Ghosn, D., & Watling, R. (2015). *Using Images in Teaching English Vocabulary: Effective Strategies for Primary School Learners. TESOL Quarterly*, 49(4), 663-673

Wang, X., & Lee, C. (2017). *The Impact of Visual Aids on Vocabulary Learning in EFL Classrooms. International Journal of Language and Linguistics*, 4(2), 1-6.

- Sunderland, J. (2000). *Issues in English Language Teaching: A Pedagogical Approach to Using Visual Aids in Vocabulary Instruction*. *ELT Journal*, 54(2), 115-123.
- Zhang, Q., & Liu, Z. (2016). *Visual Vocabulary Learning: The Role of Pictures in Language Acquisition*. *Language Teaching Research*, 20(3), 255-276.
- Allen, V. F. (1995). *Techniques in Teaching Vocabulary*. Oxford University Press.
- O'Malley, J. M., & Chamot, A. U. (1990). *Learning Strategies in Second Language Acquisition*. Cambridge University Press.
- Elwood, J. (2008). *The Role of Imagery in Vocabulary Acquisition: Theory and Practice*. *Language Education in Asia*, 3(1), 47-63.
- Miller, L., & Robinson, P. (2005). *The Effect of Visual Aids in Enhancing EFL Learners' Vocabulary Recall*. *Modern Language Journal*, 89(2), 250-264.
- Schwartz, M., & McDonald, P. (2014). *Multisensory Approaches to Vocabulary Acquisition: Combining Visual, Auditory, and Kinesthetic Learning Methods*. *Language Learning and Technology*, 18(3), 20-45.
- Coady, J., & Huckin, T. (1997). *Second Language Vocabulary Acquisition: A Rationale for Pedagogical Choices*. Cambridge University Press.